

School of Psychological Science

Examining the stress-eating relationship using cross-lagged correlations: An unexplored possibility

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Abstract

The influence of stress on eating is well-recognized, with observations of stress-induced overeating in some people and under-eating in others. However, prevalent focus on same-day stress-eating associations fails to consider the evolutionary improbability of ready availability of food during stressful events. To resolve this issue, the present study considered evolutionary predictions for adaptive behaviours and examined a previously unexplored possibility: that stress might influence intake with a delay. For this, cross-lagged correlations between daily stress and hunger (proxy measure of intake) were performed. These variables were gathered from 45 participants, using daily questionnaires lasting upto 100 days. A demographic survey also recorded participants' self-reported stress-eating response i.e. 'less than normal', 'same as normal' or 'more than normal'. The study hypothesised that stress would influence hunger with a delay of a day or two, and that such a delayed association would be moderated by participants' stress-eating responses. This hypothesis was supported and stress was found to influence hunger with a day's delay, but only for the group that reported a 'same as normal' stress-eating response. The absence of a uniform sample-wide trend corroborates previous research, while evidence for a delayed influence of stress on eating offers a new avenue for research.

An undesirable consequence of modern-day living is the increase in stress levels, which affect a large number of individuals today. The pernicious impact of stress on health behaviours and outcomes is well established (Dougall & Baum, 2001). One of its clearest effects, however, is that on eating behaviour (Groesz et. al, 2012). Surveys reveal that, when stressed some people lose their appetite while others report a greater desire for food (for e.g., Kandiah, Yake & Willett, 2008). Similar findings have also been observed in empirical studies – where some people are observed to reduce food intake under stress, while others increase it (Wallis & Hetherington, 2009; Oliver, & Wardle,1999). Till date, most studies on the stress-eating relationship emphasise the ‘individual differences’ model, which identifies why certain individuals for e.g., restrained eaters (Lattimore & Caswell, 2004) and emotional eaters (Wallis & Hetherington, 2009) might be more likely to increase intake in response to stress. However, there is no overarching framework that can predict the direction of stress-induced eating in the population, as a whole (Wardle, Steptoe, Oliver & Lipsey, 2000). With this in mind, when we consider the harmful effects of repeated stress-induced eating on the overall health of an individual — especially in conditions like obesity, cardiovascular disease and depression — then, understanding how stress affects eating appears rather critical from a public health perspective (Björntorp, 2001).

The absence of a predictable pattern in stress-induced eating might imply two things. First, it could reflect certain inherent differences in people’s psychophysiological response to stress (for example, differences in cortisol reactivity) that influence eating behaviours that follow the stress response (Epel, Lapidus, McEwen & Brownell, 2001). Secondly, the exclusive focus on same-day associations between stress and eating (which is observed across most studies on the subject, till date), is equally likely to play a part in the limited understanding about general mechanisms that predict the direction of change in stress-induced eating i.e. whether people eat less or more when stressed (for e.g., Lattimore & Caswell, 2004). This is because, in

attempting to explain an almost immediate increase in dietary intake in response to experimentally-induced stress, such studies often fail to consider the evolutionary improbability of having readily available food to be accessed in stressful situations (Belovsky, 1988). A prime contention then, is that such a response is likely to be an artefact of the modern environment and its influence, rather than an evolved adaptation to deal with stress (De Ridder & van den Bos, 2006). To better understand adaptive mechanisms that could be regulating stress-eating associations, our paper examines evolutionary reasoning to suggest an alternative, and previously unexplored possibility: that stress might influence intake with a delay of a day or two.

Predominantly, stressors are of two types: short-term (acute stress) and daily-occurring (chronic stress). In our ancestral environment, acute stressors would have required a speedy fight-or-flight response, so energy needed to be directed towards the brain and muscle tissues (Adam & Epel, 2007). Indeed, in the immediate aftermath of a stressful event, corticotropin-releasing-hormone is released into the blood stream, which mediates a suppression of food intake; and thereby promotes a diversion of bodily resources away from less urgent needs – such as food intake, digestion and reproduction – to prioritise fight, flight, or withdrawal behaviours (Majzoub, 2006). The expectation then, would be for normal eaters i.e. “normal-weight persons whose emotional and restrained eating scores fall within the normal range”, to lower food intake when they experience acute stress (Macht, 2008, p.4). However, laboratory studies examining the impact of acute stress on eating among normal eaters, show evidence for both stress-induced hyperphagia (excessive eating) and under-eating (for review, see Adam & Epel, 2007).

A key issue with such studies is that they exclusively examine same-day associations between stress and intake, thus any compensations for food intake of the previous day/days are likely to be overlooked. This is an important consideration because research has previously

demonstrated that the human body is able to regulate energy by attuning energy expenditure to energy intake and vice versa (Hill, Melanson & Wyatt, 2000). The fact that in most people, body weight is maintained at a fairly unchanging level across several years suggests this to be the case (Bouchard & Tremblay, 1997). However, for regulation to take place, there need to be compensatory mechanisms available to adjust energy intake in response to a surfeit or deficit from prior day/days (De Castro & Plunkett, 2002). And indeed, previous research has shown that physiological variables affecting intake appear to feed back after a minimum of a day's delay and often longer, to modify the overall extent of intake bias (De Castro, 1988).

Relatedly, modern-day humans are not exempt from chronic stress either. Chronic stress is known to elicit a more passive hypothalamic–pituitary–adrenal (HPA) axis-driven response, accompanied by surges in cortisol which could encourage people to consume calorie-dense foods (Rutters et al., 2012). However, a longitudinal study of people's response to everyday stresses revealed that the majority of individuals are much more likely to eat less than normal in response to daily stresses (Stone & Brownell, 1994). Here too, however, a central limitation is the exclusive focus on same-day correlations between stress and food intake, making it unlikely to account for any compensatory effects.

To better understand why an exclusive focus on same-day correlations between stress and intake could be problematic in understanding the potential mechanisms that underlie directional changes in stress-induced eating, it is useful to look at evolutionary predictions for optimal feeding behaviours. It is important to consider that, for approximately 90% of the ~1.8 million years of human existence, human survival was dependent on the ability to forage for food. Thus, food insecurity is likely to have been a major source of stress in our ancestral environment (Brunstrom & Cheon, 2018). One way in which our ancestors protected themselves from food insecurity was by coexisting in close social networks – so if one person was rendered unfit for foraging (say through injury) then others could assume the task

(Belovsky, 1988). It has been argued that in such food-sharing arrangements, social status and economic resources likely served as means to gain access to food, and this could in turn produce a psychological overlap of security for calories and socioeconomic resources (Briers & Laporte, 2013; Cheon & Hong, 2017). Consistent with this idea, laboratory studies have noted that even briefly inducing a state of insecurity about one's subjective socio-economic status (Cheon, & Hong, 2017), or a perception of unequal resources in comparison to others (Sim, Lim, Forde, & Cheon, 2018) brings about an increase in self-selected food portions, actual energy intake and preference for calorically-dense foods. Likewise, even psychosocial stress would have indicated fluctuations in social food-sharing networks and by implication, in food distribution and security (Gurven, Jaeggi, von Rueden, Hooper & Kaplan, 2015). Indeed, psychosocial stress is found to promote increases in food intake (see Epel, Lapidus, McEwen & Brownell, 2001). In subsistence populations too (where the typical socioecological conditions closely parallel those that prevailed across most of human evolutionary history) — psychological health, food anxiety and subsistence productivity, are found closely associated (Stieglitz et al. 2014).

Following from these arguments, a recent suggestion is that perhaps an evolutionary function of stress could be to facilitate a kind of ‘insurance eating’ when a threat to physical stores of energy is perceived, particularly in environments where resources are scarce or unpredictable (Brunstrom, & Cheon, 2018). Initial evidence for this idea came from non-human animal literature — with observations of increased food intake among captive birds (Fokidis et. al, 2012), greenfinches (Ekman & Hake, 1990) and overwintering birds (Rogers, 2015) on exposure to states of resource uncertainty. A similar form of ‘insurance eating’ has also been observed in humans. For example, an anticipated period of fasting has been found to increase food intake (Eldredge, Agras, & Arnow, 1994) and in Minnesota Starvation Experiment, participants continued to overeat even after returning to their initial bodyweight

(Müller et al., 2015). However, the greater part of the research on insurance eating, has focused on how exposures to cues of food insecurity (or those that would have at least, historically, served as reliable cues of resource uncertainty) lead to weight gain in present-day humans (Nettle, Andrews & Bateson, 2017). From an evolutionary perspective, the issue with such claims is that fluctuations in food availability are likely to have occurred over shorter time scales too, presumably lesser than the time it takes for substantial weight gain to occur (Blackwell, 2017).

If such is the case, then there are liable to be several involuntary and largely unconscious pathways by which events that historically predicted food scarcity would guide increases in energy intake, shifts in energy expenditure and perhaps, changes in food preference. Here, a special role has been suggested for the HPA axis activation and subsequent release of glucocorticoids - a key physiological response to stress and injury (Blackwell, 2017). Both are known to induce an increase in energy intake as well as expenditure, particularly when stress is chronic (Nettle, Andrews & Bateson, 2017). Moreover, glucocorticoids are elevated in the bloodstream hours to days after a stressful event (e.g., infection, bereavement) (Sominsky & Spencer, 2014). Thus, it is likely that through most of human evolutionary history, glucocorticoids reliably signalled an increase in both, energy needs and energy unpredictability (Tataranni et al. 1996). An implication of such HPA activation would be that triggers other than food security threats which frequently produced a glucocorticoid response, would also be able to affect appetite. However, among humans in modern societies, there is likely to be little association between HPA activation and a food security threat; yet such stressors could lead to changes in energy uptake which may not be complemented by changes in energy expenditure or resource uncertainty (Blackwell, 2017).

Moreover, it is important to bear in mind that emotional states (for e.g., acute stress) do not occur in isolation but against a backdrop of prevailing mood; and emotional states and

mood have both been found to interact with food intake (Singh, 2014). Particularly relevant to the present study is a recent finding where the authors examined momentary fluctuations in mood and concluded that instead of being dictated by a singular episode, mood appeared to operate as a monitor of a combined momentum of experiences to assess whether outcomes were turning out worse or better than anticipated (Rutledge, Skandali, Dayan & Dolan, 2014). In viewing this finding from an evolutionary perspective, one study suggested that mood can be considered an adaptive mechanism serving multiple functions, one being that of improving efficiency in foraging by keeping a track of successes over time rather than depending on singular encounters (Eldar, Rutledge, Dolan & Niv, 2016). Expanding on this, Brunstrom and Cheon (2018) suggest that just as acute stress influences appetite in people, mood might serve a similar function of moderating foraging behaviours, but perhaps over longer periods. In other words, it is likely that day-to-day changes in perception of stress (including exposures to cues that would have indicated food insecurity) are monitored by mood, which historically, is likely to have aided efficiency in foraging by promoting decisions to relocate to different foraging locations or to encourage increased energy intake when an aggregative of recent experiences suggested that prospects for food have progressed worse than expected (Brunstrom & Cheon, 2018). Framed this way, one can see how day-to-day changes in stress might then feed on to mood, and therefore influence intake with a delay of a few days.

However, till date, most studies that have assessed associations between stress and food intake, have either examined the relationship within the same day, or across several months or years (albeit indirectly, by using weight gain as proxy for long-term food intake). To date, only one study has investigated the role of time-lags (or delays longer than a day) in associations between foods and moods; and it concluded that food influences mood with a lag of 2 days (Hendy, 2012). However, this study concerned itself with the relationship between food and negative mood in general, which encompasses several emotional states like anger, fear,

nervousness, in addition to stress. Taken separately, each of these emotions are known to differ in their effect on intake (Izard, 1993; Macht, 1999).

Thus, no study to date appears to have investigated the more nuanced topic of whether or not stress influences food intake with a delay of a day or two. To examine this possibility, the present study will employ a naturalistic, longitudinal design, where the variables would be recorded using a 24-hour recall, self-report method. Since stress is a difficult concept to define operationally (Monroe, 2008), an open-ended question will be employed to examine participant's perception of stress, which would serve as the first key variable. For the second variable, hunger would be used a proxy measure for food intake since (i) hunger has previously proven a useful predictor of spontaneous total energy intake in free-living humans (Drapeau et. al, 2007) and, (ii) recording daily intakes over several weeks is often difficult and results in several inaccuracies (Samuelson, 2000). Additionally, previous research has consistently observed individual differences in stress-eating responses (i.e. same as normal/less than normal/ more than normal) and these responses appear to remain fairly stable over time (Stone & Brownell, 1994) and across varied stressors (Lattimore & Caswell, 2004). Since such individual differences were equally likely to moderate the possibility of a lagged-relationship between stress and hunger, people's subjective-reports of their stress-eating responses would serve as a third key variable. Overall, the present study hypothesises that stress would have a delayed influence on hunger (delayed by one or two days), and that the presence/absence of such a delayed relationship would be moderated by participants' stress-eating responses.

Methods

Participants

Seventy participants (55 women and 15 men) were recruited by five researchers from personal contacts and the University of Bristol. The recruitment was carried out in two phases. In the first phase, 52 participants were enrolled. However, six weeks after the study first began, an additional 18 participants were recruited. This was done to in anticipation of a low response rate due to requirements of daily participation lasting several weeks.

Exclusion criteria for the study included: 1) age < 18 years; 2) being pregnant or planning a pregnancy; 3) having diabetes; 4) having a history of eating disorders; and 5) being on appetite-influencing medications (except oral contraceptives). All participants provided informed consent for partaking in the study and ethical approval was granted by the institutional review board at the University of Bristol.

Materials and procedure

Two questionnaires were used to obtain the necessary data and both were created for this study.

Daily Questionnaire

Participants were required to complete a daily, online questionnaire, which took about a minute to complete. They were instructed to respond as close to 7 p.m. as possible and no later than midnight; preferably at the same time each day. To ensure compliance, participants were sent a daily text reminder at 7 p.m. The questionnaire was created and hosted on the Gorilla Experiment Builder (Anwyl-Irvine, Massonnié, Flitton, Kirkham & Evershed, 2019) and could be accessed using a phone, tablet or PC. To complete the questionnaire, participants were instructed to mentally review their day and answer six questions (see Table 1). These questions were designed to capture participant's assessment of their general feelings of hunger, thirst,

cravings for unhealthy foods, perceived emotional closeness to friends and family, stress levels and subjective social status, on the particular day. At a time, only one question appeared on the screen and the question order was randomised to avoid ordering bias.

For the first five of the six questions shown in Table 1, participants indicated their answers on a sliding scale i.e., by moving the handle of the slider from its default central position towards one of the two extremes of the scale. For example, in response to the question “How stressed have felt today?”, participants indicated their rating by selecting any point on the scale between the end points “Not at all stressed” and “Extremely stressed” (see last column, Table 1). The scores in the sliding scale ranged from 0 to 100, but they were not visible to the participants. Each question was further accompanied by a relevant picture to better illustrate the context. However, for the sixth measure — subjective social status — participants were instead presented with a pictorial version of the MacArthur Scale of Subjective Social Status (Goldman, Cornman & Chang, 2006) which comprised an image of 10-rung ladder, on which participants had to indicate the rung that they felt they stood at relative to others in their social groups. The data for this variable was calculated by assessing the vertical distance between the bottom of the ladder and the selected rung. Overall, this questionnaire was completed for 100 days by the participants who were recruited in the first phase of the study, while those recruited in the second phase completed it for 59 days.

Table 1. *The table indicates the details for questions asked in the daily questionnaire.*

Variable	Question	Response Range
1. Stress	“How stressed have you felt today”?	Not at all stressed / Extremely stressed
2. Hunger	“How hungry have you felt today”	Not at all hungry / Extremely hungry

3. Thirst	“How thirsty have you felt today?”	Not at all thirsty / Extremely thirsty
4. Unhealthy Food Cravings	“Have you craved unhealthy foods today”?	Not at all / Extremely
5. Connection to friends and family	“Have you felt a close connection with friends and family?”	Detached and Isolated / Very closely connected
6. Subjective Social Status	“Think of yourself relative to others in your local community, workplace, social groups etc. Now place yourself on a ladder. People who have higher standing than others, they are more successful and at the top. Think about how have you felt today? Where would you place yourself on this ladder?”	Position on the displayed ladder (i.e. pictorial depiction of the MacArthur Scale of Subjective Social Status)

Demographic Survey

Two weeks after the daily questionnaires were terminated, participants were given an online survey to complete. They were asked to report their birthdates, ethnicity, tertiary education (number of post-16 years of education), body weight and height. The height and weight measures were used to evaluate body mass index ($BMI = \text{kg/m}^2$), a surrogate measure of body fat (Who, 2004). Dietary restraint was measured with three items from the Three Factor Eating Questionnaire (Karlsson, Persson, Sjöström, & Sullivan, 2000), which comprised the following sentences: “I deliberately take small helpings to control my weight...”, “I don’t eat some foods because they make me fat” and “I consciously hold back on how much I eat at

meals to keep from gaining weight...”. Responses were made using a four-point rating for each item (1 = definitely false, 2 = mostly false, 3= mostly true, 4= definitely) and the sum of ratings for all three items was used as the dietary restraint score. Similarly, in response to the question “When I feel sad I often eat too much...?”, participants could answer using an identical four-point rating provided for the dietary restraint items. A question was also asked about attempts to diet over the last 12 months to lose weight, to which participants had to respond by choosing among the options: “None”, “Once” or “Twice or more”. Moreover, the survey included one item to assess participant’s perceived influence of stress on their eating i.e. “stress-eating response”. For this, they responded to the statement: “After a very stressful day I often eat...”, with the answer categories: “less than normal”, “more than normal” or “same as normal”. Lastly, participants were asked to give a rating of 1-5 stars as to how easy they found the experiment.

Data reduction and stress-hunger hypothesis

Prior to the analysis, one participant was excluded for providing an unchanging stress response throughout the experiment. Subsequent data was analysed in two phases. In the first phase, cross-lagged correlations were calculated. Such correlations are used to test the possibility of a time-lagged association between two variables, and involve correlating two variables, each at a different time-point than the other (and the difference between the time-points is known as the time-lag). Generally, the time-lag with the highest correlation coefficient is regarded as the true time-lag between two variables. Accordingly, cross-lagged correlations were performed for each participant (two variables at a time) across all possible pairings between the variables - hunger, unhealthy food cravings, stress, closeness, thirst and social status. More specifically, Pearson’s correlation coefficients (which ranged from -1 to +1) were calculated for each variable pair, with time-lags extending from -7 to +7 days, resulting in 15 such coefficients for each participant. Since the cross-correlations extended across time-lags

of up to 7 days, only those participants ($n=48$) who completed the daily questionnaire for ≥ 8 consecutive days were included in this part of the analysis.

Specific to our hypotheses, the second phase of the analysis only included cross-lagged correlations between stress and hunger, while cross-correlations between other variables were not analysed any further. For this part of the analysis, three participants who had missing or incomplete entries on the demographic survey were excluded from further analysis, leaving 45 participants. Our main hypothesis predicted that cross-lagged correlations between stress and hunger would be higher with time-lags of 1 or 2 days, as compared to same-day correlations and that such a lagged-relationship would vary as per the self-reported stress-eating responses of the participants. This hypothesis was tested using a 3x3 mixed-model analysis of variance (ANOVA), followed by Bonferroni post-hoc tests.

All statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics Version 25.

Results

Participant Characteristics

Of the 45 participants included in the final analysis, 33 were females and 12 males (for other demographic details, see Table 2). Overall, participants completed the study for an average of 28 consecutive days and rated the average ease of completing the experiment as 3.64 out of a maximum score of 5. For dietary restraint, a split along the sample median score of six was performed. Participants scoring above six were rated as restrained eaters, while those scoring seven and above were recorded as unrestrained eaters (for final metrics, see Table 2). Importantly, a majority of our participants reported to stress affecting their overall food intake, with 29% reporting to eat less than normal and 49% reporting to eat more than normal when stressed; while 22% of participants claimed to eating same as normal in response to stress.

Table 2. *Demographic background and characteristics of the sample*

Characteristics	n	%	Mean	S.D.
Age	45		23.80	6.07
BMI (kg/m ²)	45		22.09	3.96
Ethnicity				
Asian/Asian British		56%		
White		40%		
Other Ethnic Groups		4%		
Years of Education				
≥ 19 years		95.5%		
< 19 years		4.5%		
Diet attempts in last 12 months				
None		58 %		
Once		13%		

Twice or More	29%
Dietary Restraint	
Restrained Eaters	44%
Unrestrained Eaters	56%

Relationship between stress and hunger

Data were analysed using a 3x3 mixed-design ANOVA with a within-subjects factor of time-lags (0 lag/1-day lag/ 2-day lag), a between-subjects factor of ‘stress-eating response’ (more than normal/less than normal/same as normal), and the outcome variable of cross-lagged correlation coefficients between stress and hunger. Equal variances were assumed based upon results of the Levene’s test. However, Mauchly’s test indicated that the assumption of sphericity was violated, $\chi^2(2) = 6.90, p=.032$, therefore degrees of freedom were corrected using Huynh-Feldt estimates of sphericity ($\epsilon = .94$).

The results revealed a significant main effect of time-lag $F(1.89, 79.19) = 3.32, p=0.044, \eta_p^2=.073$. However, pairwise comparisons revealed that for the sample as whole, coefficients did not vary significantly between lags of 0, 1 and 2 days (see last column of Table 3). A significant main effect of stress-eating response $F(2, 42) = 4.89, p=0.012, \eta_p^2=.189$ was also found.

Table 3. Means of Pearson’s correlation coefficients between stress and hunger, collapsed across different stress-eating response and time-lags (S.D.)

Stress-Eating	Less than normal	Same as normal	More than normal	Total
Time Lag (days)				
0	.07 (.25)	-.18 (.25)	-.09 (.26)	-.06 (.27)
1	.08 (.15)	.12 (.30)	-.12 (.22)	-.01 (.25)
2	.08 (.20)	.12 (.29)	-.09 (.19)	.01 (.23)

More important, there was a significant interaction between stress eating response and time-lag $F(3.77, 79.19) = 3.04, p = 0.024, \eta^2 = .127$. To follow up this interaction, post hoc comparisons using the Bonferroni test were carried out. Importantly, we were interested to see whether or not people with different stress-eating responses would show a lagged relationship between stress and hunger i.e. have higher coefficient means for a 1- or 2-day lag, as compared to 0 lag. As can be seen in the Figure 1, for the group who reported their stress-eating response to be same as normal, we found a significant mean increase ($p = 0.002$) in the stress-hunger correlation coefficient by an average of .298, 95% C.I. [-.50, -.10] between 0 lag and 1 day lag; while the correlation coefficients between stress and hunger did not vary significantly between 1-day and 2-day lags. However, for the other two groups i.e., those who reported eating less than normal or more than normal in response to stress, the stress-hunger correlation coefficients did not significantly differ across the three time-lags.

Figure 1. *Estimated marginal means for the interaction between groups with different stress-eating responses across different time-lags (in days) on stress-hunger cross-correlation coefficients.*

Discussion

The aim of this longitudinal study was to examine the possibility of a delayed influence of stress on intake. Based upon evolutionary reasoning, the present study hypothesised that stress would have a delayed influence on hunger (i.e. a proxy measure for intake), with a lag of a day or two, and that the absence or presence of such a delayed effect might differ on the basis of participants' subjective reports of their stress-eating responses. Indeed, the hypothesis was supported by the study's results and a significant cross-correlation between stress and hunger with a lag of one day was found, but only for the group that reported normal levels of stress-eating (i.e. those who claimed to eat same as normal in response to stress).

The absence of a common trend in the stress-hunger associations amongst the sample as whole, is consistent with previous studies that have repeatedly demonstrated the lack of a generalizable trend in the stress-eating relationship among the population as a whole (Wardle, Steptoe, Oliver & Lipsey, 2000). To explain such disparate stress-eating tendencies in the population, several studies have implicated individual differences in eating behaviours like levels of restrained eating (Lattimore & Caswell, 2004) or emotional eating (Wallis & Hetherington, 2009), while others have suggested a role for differences in people's psychophysiological responses to stress (Epel, Lapidus, McEwen & Brownell, 2001).

However, in the group that reported normal levels of stress-eating, the present study did find significant cross-lagged correlations between stress and hunger. In other words, the results demonstrated that those who claimed to not consciously restrict their intake or overeat in response to stress, showed subsequently increased hunger levels following a stressful day. And even though, the observed correlation was fairly modest, it is nonetheless noteworthy since the lagged effects of stress on hunger fell in line with evolutionary theory and can be interpreted in two ways.

The first interpretation of the varying trends in stress-intake associations found among those with different stress-eating responses, involves evolutionary predictions for optimal foraging. Evolutionary models suggest that our feeding behaviours are likely to have been modified by natural selection towards achieving specific goals (i.e., preventing starvation, energy maximisation) while functioning within certain constraints (e.g., evading predators, maintaining social status) (Brunstrom, & Cheon, 2018). To understand our results from this perspective, it is useful to first take stock of the two groups who did not show a significant delayed influence of stress on hunger. For example, consider the strategy of the group who reported to eating more than normal when stressed. Evolutionarily, such conscious overeating in response to stress is unlikely to have been a common response among our foraging ancestors, simply due to the lack of readily available food for access at will (Belovsky, 1988). Equally, authors have argued that conscious restriction of food, even on a stressful day is unlikely to have been an adaptive strategy, since such restriction would likely compete with deeply engrained biological and behavioural adaptations that protected against starvation and facilitated our historic foraging abilities (Appelhans, 2009). And this strategy can be likened to the group who reported eating less than normal on stressful days, especially since such under-eating appears to be a conscious phenomenon. On this basis, it can be speculated that the group who reported a normal stress-eating response (i.e. demonstrated no conscious increase or decrease in intake in response to stress) were likely operating in a way that was guided less by the modern influences of immediately accessible foods and more along unconscious mechanisms; moreover, such behaviour was consistent with the present hypothesis based on evolutionary predictions for adaptive stress-eating behaviour. However, when addressing the broad question of how feeding behaviours of ‘modern humans’ operate within current food environments, it would be important to ascertain whether mechanisms that supported efficient foraging in our ancestors, are truly preserved and expressed in the modern

man (Illius, Tolkamp & Yearsley, 2002). This presents a rather difficult task, especially because several of our food-related responses take place outside of conscious awareness - likely because they developed prior to the emergence of language (Searle & Willis, 2002).

A second interpretation could be that perhaps there are individual differences in the psychobiological mechanisms which guide stress-induced changes in food intake. For instance, studies investigating biological indicators of stress have demonstrated that women who show higher cortisol reactivity to stress consume more calories when stressed compared to those with lower cortisol reactivity (Epel, Lapidus, McEwen & Brownell, 2001). Similarly, individuals who report eating more under stress are more likely to be restrained eaters (Lattimore & Caswell, 2004), emotional eaters (Wallis & Hetherington, 2009), dieters (Hou et. al, 2013), women (Habhab, Sheldon & Loeb, 2009) and those who are overweight according to BMI guidelines (Laitinen, Ek & Sovio, 2002) than their respective counterparts. Since these variables were not separately analysed for in the present study, it is likely that some of the divergences observed in our results are likely a consequence of such underlying differences.

An important observation in the present study comprised the counter-intuitive results of the same-day stress-hunger correlations for individuals who reported eating either less than or more than normal in response to stress. Since we had used hunger as a proxy measure for overall intake through the day —on a stressful day — we would expect individuals who eat less than normal under stress, to be hungrier i.e. show a negative correlation between stress and hunger. Equally, we would expect those who generally eat more than normal when stressed, to show positive same-day correlations between stress and hunger. However, we found the exact opposite trend when assessing the same-day correlations for these groups. This paradox perhaps reflects the possibility that people may themselves not be too aware of their patterns of stress-induced eating. This possibility stems from the observation that among the primary psychological causes of stress-induced eating are — (i) a diminished ability to separate hunger

cues from emotional arousal, and (ii) poor awareness of one's internal physiological states (Royal & Kurtz, 2010). Previous studies have also demonstrated individual differences in people's degree of behavioural awareness, especially among those exhibiting maladaptive forms of stress-induced eating (Mann & Ward, 2004). Since the present study did not involve a behavioural awareness component to the investigation, the extent of its role cannot be commented on.

Of course, the interpretation of current results is limited by the subjective nature of variables used. In the present study, a key variable assessed was participants' subjective report of how stress affected their eating, and the veracity of such responses cannot be unequivocally assumed. However, aggregating participants' stress-eating response revealed 49% reporting stress-induced hyperphagia and 29% reporting eating less, which is comparable, although slightly below subjective-reports from previous studies which indicate a divide of 42% and 38%, respectively (Oliver & Wardle, 1999). However, the present study's figures for prevalence of stress-induced hyperphagia are markedly higher than those revealed by a longitudinal study by Stone and Brownell (1994). In that study, participants made daily ratings for a period of 84 days, of whether they had eaten less than, same as, or more than usual, in response to stress, and only 28% participants reported eating more than usual on stressful days. One justification for the difference between our results and those of Stone and Brownell's (1994) study can be attributed to methodological differences, since discrepancies between subjective records and daily reports are often noted in several facets of behaviour such as pain, sleep onset latency and premenstrual tension (Oliver & Wardle, 1999).

Overall, the present findings should be interpreted in context of some methodological constraints. First, as in all longitudinal studies, the elongated time-frame of the study necessitated exclusive reliance on self-report measures. This reflects a general difficulty of large naturalistic studies: what is gained in understanding trends over longer timeframes is

often lost in the complexity and number of measures that it is possible to administer (Farrington, 1991). Secondly, the use of a less than optimal method to measure hunger is one such limitation. Hunger was measured via a single question on participant's general perception of hunger through the day and as such, could be an insufficient probe. Lastly, the arbitrary decision of choosing 100 days as the length of the survey is likely to have limitations of its own since all survey methods are ultimately dependent on the motivation and compliance of participants, both of which are known to rapidly decline over time (De Castro, 1994). Therefore, the requirement of elongated participation in the study is likely to have been a factor in the small sample size that completed the study for a minimum of 8 consecutive days. However, on average the present study found participants to complete the study for 28 consecutive days and this time-frame can serve as a good reference point for future studies employing a similar design.

Given the limitations of this study, future work determining whether these findings can be replicated amongst larger cohorts would be valuable. Additionally, it could be useful to employ cross-lagged panel models to test for the possibility of lagged influence of stress on hunger, with the additional advantage of including some key variables likely to operate as potential confounders, e.g., levels of dietary restraint, emotional eating, BMI and dieting status (Selig & Little, 2012). Similarly, to detect predictors and outcomes associated with the stress–eating relationship, innovative and sophisticated methodologies like ecological momentary assessment (which entails repeated sampling of participants' ongoing behaviours and experiences in their natural environments, in real time) could be employed (Stone & Shiffman, 1994). These methods could provide further reliability and validity in studying the role of time-lags in the relationship between stress and intake.

A key merit of the current study was its longitudinal design, which allowed the complexity of the real world to be captured, in turn producing an unmoderated picture of the stress-intake

interaction as it unfolds. Such a design offsets the limitations inherent in previous experimental research examining the stress-eating connection, in that experimentally-induced stress may not reflect the kind of ecological validity required to gauge the true effect of stress on eating, since many real-world facilitatory influences on eating (for e.g., weekly rhythms, social facilitation) are controlled or removed (Yau & Potenza, 2013). More importantly, our study adds to the literature on self-reported effects of everyday stressors on eating, by examining a previously unexplored possibility of a lagged influence of stress on eating. Equally, the present emphasis on evolutionary predictions for understanding stress-induced eating offers a useful avenue that remains relatively understated among contemporary accounts of the stress-eating relationship.

In conclusion, the present results are of particular importance because the study is among the first attempts to investigate cross-lagged correlations between stress and hunger (by token, intake levels). Our findings suggest that, among people who self-report to eating same as normal under stressful conditions, stress appears to have a delayed influence on hunger (delayed by at least a day). By demonstrating the lack of a consistent pattern in groups with different levels of stress-induced eating, our study corroborates previous research that has demonstrated the moderating role of individual differences in the stress-eating relationship. Lastly, even though the exact causality and mechanisms underlying the directional associations between stress and intake are currently unknown, support for the previously unexamined trend of a delayed influence of stress on eating offers a new avenue for exploration.

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